

**GLOBAL MINDEDNESS OF THE PROFESSIONAL COLLEGE TEACHERS:
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Introduction

The issues of globalization and cultural diversity have gained increasing attention in higher education. As the international community moves toward greater interdependence, globalization is driving a revolution in educational institutions. Higher educational institutions have stepped up to the challenge by internationalizing their curriculum and offering education abroad opportunities for their students. The metamorphic change has been a challenge for educators and researchers to measure this cadre of globalization among higher education. The understanding that the India must play a key role in this global competitive market is felt throughout policymakers and the public. Therefore, it is imperative that the educational sector take the lead in this initiative. The workforce of tomorrow must be globally aware and culturally sensitive to create the culture of interconnectedness.

Students of today and tomorrow need to be prepared to be responsible citizens of the world, to both engage in and at the same time be critical of globalization. The promotion of global mindedness in students is one important way that they will be prepared to be responsible citizens in an era of globalization. To help students become internationally minded, we need to help teachers also become internationally minded, and we need to prepare them to teach in a way that supports their students' international-mindedness development.

Global mindedness is a touchy term that is conceptualized differently by different scholars, depending on their turned. It means seeing oneself as being interconnected with world community and feeling a sense of responsibility for members of that community. This is reflected in the individual's attitudes, beliefs, and behaviors. According to Hett (1993), the term global-mindedness denote a worldview in which an individual perceives his or herself as connected to the world community and is aware of his or her responsibility for its member responsibility for its members.

Significance of the Study

Teacher and teaching programs require attention to the rapid changes in the world, in part because populations are becoming increasingly diverse. The rapidly changing classroom environments have prompted a need to train teachers who can communicate with and teach students from increasingly diverse backgrounds.

The primary goal of education is to prepare students for work and citizenship, a goal that requires a global perspective more encompassing than that provided in a 20th century education. A growing amount of research indicates that the decisions teachers make and work that they do is based on their perspectives and thinking; therefore, the present research was conducted to examine those who do perceive that they are globally aware to what they attribute their development of a global mind is warranted to contribute to the body of knowledge in global education

In today's increasingly interconnected world, it has never been more imperative for Indian Education Systems to incorporate global education into their curriculum. As we prepare students for their future roles as global citizens who must confront a whole host of new challenges, it is critical that our students understand other cultures and people and respect and acknowledge divergent perspectives. We

need teachers who are global minded in true sense who can transact the curriculum effectively so that we can meet the objectives of becoming world citizens.

This study will be significant for the teachers of different professions to realize their own mind set about the world and how they can prepare their students to possess world minds. It might help the teachers to develop a relationship with international scholars. It also will help the educational authorities to understand the current status of global mindedness of teachers and provide with the enormous opportunities to the teachers of different professions to enhance their global perspectives and to keep healthy attitudes towards the planet earth.

The results from this study will provide the researchers a more conclusive overview of the global mindedness of teachers of different professions and the possible implications that impact this view. The participants' perspectives will have implications on professional education programs and future research. Lastly, the educational authorities and policy makers can also utilize this data to implement pedagogies in Higher education Systems to enhance global mindedness in teachers.

Objectives of the Study

The present study was designed with a view to fulfilling the following objectives based on the major research questions:

1. To study and compare the global mindedness of teachers of the following professions –
 - a) Teacher Education, and b) Management Studies
2. To study and compare the global mindedness of teachers of the following professions, on the basis of their gender.
 - a) Teacher Education, and b) Management Studies
3. To study and compare the global mindedness of teachers of the following professions, on the basis of teaching experience.
 - a) Teacher Education, and b) Management Studies
4. To study and compare the global mindedness amongst the teachers of the following professions, on the basis of the nation visited.
 - a) Teacher Education, and b) Management Studies

Operational Definitions of the Terms

The following terms used in the present study have been defined operationally.

a) Global Mindedness: In the present study global mindedness has been viewed from the following five dimensions specified by Hett (1993).

(i) **Responsibility:** A deep personal concern for people in all parts of the world which surfaces as a sense of moral responsibility to try and improve conditions in some way.

(ii) **Cultural Pluralism:** An appreciation of the diversity of cultures in the world a belief that all have something of value to offer. This is accompanied by taking pleasure in exploring and trying to understand other cultural frameworks.

(iii) **Efficacy:** A belief that an individual's actions can make a difference and that involvement in national and international issues is important.

(iv) **Global centrism:** Thinking in terms of what is good for the global community, not just what will benefit one's own country. A willingness to make judgments based on global, not ethnocentric, standards.

(v) **Interconnectedness:** An awareness and appreciation of the interrelatedness of all peoples and nations which results in a sense of global belonging or kinship with the "human family."

b) Profession: It is a paid occupation involving prolonged training and formal qualification of the individual who practices it. In the present research the teaching professions: the management studies such as business management, hotel management etc and teacher education viz. M.Ed., B.Ed., D.Ed. are taken into consideration.

c) Teacher Education: It is a teaching profession meant for preparing teachers for different levels. The teachers who prepare teachers or teach at different levels are known as teacher educators. For the present research the D.Ed., B.Ed. and M.Ed. teachers are considered.

d) Management Studies: This is defined as the professional courses such as business management, hotel management etc the individuals pursues to get into a profession in future based upon these courses.

e) Gender: It refers to biological, physiological and social characteristics that define human being as men or women.

f) Teaching Experience: The period of teaching served by each individual teacher has been considered as teaching experience. The teaching experience of the teachers in both the professional institutions divided into three categories such as 1 to 5 years, 6 to 10 years and above 10 years.

g) Nation(s) Visited: It is defined as the teachers who have been to one or more nations on accounts of vacation, study tours, cultural exchange programmes, higher studies or research. The comparison among the teachers in their global mindedness has been done on the basis of the teachers who have been and who have never been to different nations.

Hypotheses of the Study

Based on the objectives stated above for the study, the following hypotheses were formulated.

1. There exists no statistically significant difference between teacher educators and management teachers in their global mindedness.
2. There exists no statistically significant difference between male and female teachers of the following teaching professions in their global mindedness-
 - a) Teacher Education, and b) Management Studies
3. There exist no statistically significant differences among the teachers with various levels of teaching experience of the following teaching professions in their global mindedness -
 - a) Teacher Education, and b) Management Studies
4. There exists no statistically significant difference between the teachers who have visited nations and who have not visited of the following teaching professions in their global mindedness-
 - a) Teacher Education, and b) Management Studies

Delimitations of the Study

The study on global mindedness was delimited to teachers from management studies and teacher education institutions affiliated to university of Mumbai. The study was also delimited to Navi Mumbai, Maharashtra.

Review of Literature

It was observed through the reviews of literature that overall; the literature is newly emerging with several unresolved issues. Literature devoted to the development of international-mindedness is exceptionally scarce. As Haywood (2007) argues, 'The literature is scanty as regards research to identify hard learning outcomes'. Surprisingly, there are hardly any research has conducted to measure the global mindedness of teachers or students.

Many scholars contributing to the literature base lack empirical evidence to support their proposals. Specifically, more research is necessary that focuses on developing curricula and assessment practices of which international mindedness is an intrinsic part - even if this just means clearly underscoring the difficulties in providing answers. More empirical research could also work towards validating, contesting or extending existing theories on international-mindedness. It would enable some of the unresolved debates on international-mindedness to become constructive ideas that can encourage social consensus in the field of international education and our global thinking.

It was observed that most of the researches on global mindedness have been conducted on students viz Guffey (2012), DeMello (2011), Gail Zahn, Elizabeth Sandell, and Caryn Lindsay(2004), Sleeter,

Zeichner., Park., Hoban, & Sorensen (2011), Deng and Boatler (1993) and Hinrichs (2002, 2003). Studies carried out by Nancy Gallavan (2008), Golay (2006), and Acolatse(2002) were conducted on student teachers and study abroad students with other variables. No study was found to be conducted on teachers of different professions. Thus, researches on global mindedness of teachers need to be conducted to explore it as the teachers play a pivotal role in the preparation of students to face the world and in developing in them the right kind of attitude towards the world.

Methodology

a) Research Method

In order to assure the smooth functioning and properly carrying out of a particular research project, a researcher is required to select an appropriate research method. Selection of a research method depends upon the nature of research, the objectives and hypotheses of the study. Keeping these in mind the researcher used Descriptive Comparative Survey method in conducting the present study.

b) Population and Selection of Sample

The accessible population of the study considered of all the teacher educators (M.Ed., B.Ed., & D.Ed.) and teachers at various management studies in Navi Mumbai, Maharashtra.

The sample for the study was selected using stratified random sampling technique. The teachers from both the teaching professions were classified on the basis of their gender, teaching experience and different nations visited and not visited by them.

The data producing sample of teachers from both the teaching professions consists of 335. However, out of 335 teachers had 34 teachers had returned the data sheet incomplete. Hence, the actual data producing sample was reduced to 301. Out of 301 teachers 150 were male (99 teachers from management institutions and 51 from teacher education institutions) and 151 were females (72 teachers from management institutions and 79 from teacher education institutions).

c) The Tools and Techniques Used For the Present Study

The Global Minded Scale was employed to collect the necessary data for the study. The tool was developed by the researcher based on Hett's 'Global Minded Scale'. It was updated/modified keeping Indian scenario in mind. The detail description of the tool and techniques used are given in the following paragraphs.

The Global Mindedness Scale was developed, validated and used by the researcher in order to understand clearly the global mindedness of teachers belonging to the teaching professions of management studies and teacher education. For the present study the tool has been validated as is evident from the manner it was developed by the investigator and examined by the experts.

The reliability of the tool was established by split-half method. The reliability co-efficient of the global minded scale was 0.85, which means it was a highly reliable tool. In the way the final forms of the tool prepared ready.

The five point Likert Scale such as Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (UD), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) was used. The respondents were asked to put (√) against each statement. There were around 35 statements in the Global Minded Scale. Mostly the statements were positive. The example of the statements is; the world is generally a fair place (global justice and disparities), I think in terms of giving back to the global society (global interconnectedness and personal responsibility) etc.

d) Data Collection Procedure

The researcher had to visit different colleges for the purpose of data collection. The data collection procedure was exciting as well as challenging. On the given dates, the researcher approached the teachers in a group and individually also, explained the purpose of the research, the nature of tools and requested the respondents to fill the tools sincerely and honestly. The teachers took around 30 to 40 minutes to furnish the data sheet. The researcher had approached around 335 teachers to obtain data. However, some of the

teachers returned the data sheet incomplete and a few of them did not return the same showing various reasons and time constraint. The incomplete tools were rejected.

e) Scoring and Tabulation of the Tools

The scoring was done based on the type of statement; a positive one was scored from 'strongly agree', 'agree', 'undecided', 'disagree' and 'strongly disagree' as 5, 4, 3, 2, 1 and the negative statement was scored as 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5.

3.7 Data Analysis

The obtained data was analyzed by employing statistical techniques such as Mean, Standard Deviation, Standard error of Mean, t-test and, ANOVA (One-way Analysis of Variance)

Major Findings

The major findings of the study are as follows:

1. The statistical analysis of the data revealed that the teachers from both the teaching professions - management studies and teacher education are moderately global minded.
2. Though teacher educators scored little higher than the management teachers in global mindedness but the teachers from both the teaching profession did not differ significantly in their global mindedness.
3. The female teachers from both the teaching professions found to be more global minded than the male teachers.
4. Male and female teachers from both the teaching professions (management studies and teacher education) differed significantly in their global mindedness.
5. The teachers from management studies within the teaching experience of 1 to 5 years found to be more globally minded than the teachers within 6 to 10 and above 10 years of teaching experiences.
6. The teachers from management studies with more than 10 years of teaching experience found to be less globally minded than their counterparts with 1 to 5 and 6 to 10 yrs of teaching experiences.
7. The differences among the teachers of management studies within the teaching experiences of 1 to 5, 6 to 10 and above 10 years of experiences were found not significant.
8. The teacher educators with more than 10 years teaching experiences found to be more global minded than the teacher educators with less than 10 years and within 1 to 5 years of teaching experiences.
9. There existed significant difference among the teacher educators within the 1 to 5, 6 to 10 and above 10 years of teaching experiences.
10. It was observed that the teachers from management studies who have visited different nations were little more global minded than those teachers who have not visited any nation(s). Whereas, the teachers from teacher education fields those who have visited different nations were found less global minded than their counterparts those who have not visited any nation(s)
11. There existed no significant difference between teachers (from both the teaching professions management studies and teacher education) those who have visited and those who have not visited any nation(s) in their global mindedness.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study the following conclusions were drawn.

1. The teachers irrespective of their type of teaching professions are global minded to a moderate level.
2. The area or types of teaching profession is not a factor associated with the global mindedness of teachers. Teachers from both the teaching professions (management studies and teacher education) are equal in their global mindedness.

3. Gender is a factor associated with the global mindedness of the teachers. Female teachers are more global minded than the male teachers irrespective of their area of teaching professions.
4. The years or certain periods of teaching experience is not an aspect connected with the global mindedness of teachers from management studies. The teachers within any range of years of teaching experiences are identical in their global mindedness.
5. The years or certain period of teaching experiences is influencing the global mindedness of teacher educators. Higher the years of teaching experience of a teacher higher is his or her level of global mindedness.
6. Visiting different nations or countries is not necessarily connected with the global mindedness of teachers from both the teaching professions. Teachers, those who have and those who have not visited different nation(s) are equal in their global mindedness irrespective of their area or field of teaching professions.

Implications of the Present Study

As we embark upon the twenty-first century, we realize that the world is becoming increasingly interconnected. Economic, social, and technological transformations are linking us in unprecedented ways. Yet, despite of increasing globalization, educational systems are not reflecting this phenomenon. Only a few teachers today are well prepared to educate students for this new global context. Today's students will need extensive knowledge of the world and the skills and dispositions to engage with people from many cultures and countries. They will need these to be responsible citizens and effective participants in the global marketplace of the 21st century. Hence, more researches on global mindedness of teachers need to be conducted at various levels as well as on teachers of various courses.

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